

Oxidation Mechanism of Cyclopentanone by Chloramine-T

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Mechanism of oxidation of cyclopentanone by chloramine-T in alkaline media has been reported. A first order dependence in chloramine-T, cyclopentanone and hydroxide ions has been observed. Neutral salts and p-toluene sulphonamide were found to have insignificant effect on the reaction rate while the effect of addition of methanol was negative. A mechanism involving interaction of enol anion of cyclopentanone with chloramine-T to form an intermediate in a slow step and its subsequent reaction with another molecule of chloramine-T in a fast step has been found to explain the data well. Various thermodynamic parameters have been computed. Corresponding 1,2-diketone has been reported to be the product.

EXCEPTING some recent investigations¹⁻⁶, little is known about the kinetics and mechanisms of the oxidations by chloramine-T. The present paper reports the results of our kinetic investigations on the oxidation of cyclopentanone by Chloramine-T in alkaline media. The main object has been to elucidate the reaction mechanism and put forward a rate law consistent with the experimental data.

Experimental

E. Merk, Pro analysi, sample of chloramine-T was used and the solution was stored in black coated bottle to prevent photochemical decomposition. The strength was determined using iodometric method⁷. p-toluene sulphonamide was prepared from Koch-light (England) sample. Ascorbic acid was always prepared fresh from E. Merck sample. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The reactions were carried out in Jena glass reaction bottles blackened from outside.

Kinetics was followed by estimating unconsumed chloramine-T indirectly, using ascorbic acid.⁸ Five ml. aliquot portion of the reaction mixture was quickly transferred to a titrating flask containing excess ascorbic acid and 5 ml. of 1N hydrochloric acid. The excess of ascorbic acid was then back titrated against standard chloramine-T using iodometric method.

Stoichiometry

Reaction mixture containing excess of chloramine-T over cyclopentanone was allowed to equilibrate at 55° in the presence of 0.02M NaOH. The results showed that one mole of cyclopentanone consumes two moles of chloramine-T and accordingly :

The product 1,2-diketone was tested by the positive spot test⁹.

Results

The kinetic investigations were carried out at several initial concentrations of chloramine-T and cyclopentanone at constant hydroxide ion concentration. Owing to high hydroxide ion concentration (pH ≈ 12), no buffer could be employed. First order dependence in chloramine-T was followed at all initial concentration of the reactants (Table 1) A linear increase in pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) in chloramine-T was observed with increase in cyclopentanone concentration. The average value of second order rate constants (calculated as $k_2 = k_1/[\text{Cyclopentanone}]$) were found as (1.407 ± 0.093) and $(1.724 \pm 0.067) \times 10^{-2}$ l mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ in presence of 0.02M NaOH at 35° and 40° respectively.

TABLE I
[NaOH] = 0.02M

10 ³ [Chloramine-T] M	10 ² [Cyclopentanone] M	10 ⁵ k ₁ sec ⁻¹ at	
		35°	40°
0.6	0.6	8.55	9.91
0.8	0.6	8.52	9.97
1.0	0.6	8.97	10.70
1.2	0.6	8.58	10.70
1.6	0.6	8.95	10.70
2.0	0.6	9.20	11.20
1.0	0.4	5.91	7.08
1.0	0.8	12.01	14.23
1.0	1.0	13.97	16.57
1.0	1.2	15.77	20.35
1.0	1.6	22.53	27.83

Hydroxide ion dependence : The reaction was found to be very susceptible to change in hydroxide ion concentration and, therefore, investigations were carried out at different initial concentration of hydroxide ion at constant ionic strength maintained by

0.2M sodium perchlorate. It is observed that the rate constants increase linearly with increase in hydroxide ion concentration. The order in alkali has been obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ (Fig. 1) as 1.03 and 1.04 at 35° and 40° respectively.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ [Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Cyclopentanone] = $0.6 \times 10^{-2} M$ [NaClO₄] = 0.2 M.

Effect of neutral salts, *p*-toluene sulphonamide and Methanol : Neutral salts viz., sodium perchlorate and potassium chloride were found to have negligible effect on the reaction rate. *p*-toluene sulphonamide, known to retard the chloraminometric oxidations in acidic media, has no effect while the effect of addition of methanol was negative.

Temperature dependence : To compute the thermodynamic parameters (Table 2), viz., energy of activation, frequency factor, heat of activation and entropy of activation, kinetic studies were made at five different temperatures (35°–55°)

TABLE 2

k_2 at 45° l ³ mole ⁻³ sec ⁻¹	E_A K.cal/mole	$\log A$	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
1.13 ± 1.01	8.9 ± 0.1	$6.11 \pm .01$	$8.23 \pm .02$	$-31.75 \pm .05$

Discussion

The oxidising properties of chloramine-T may be due to four oxidising species viz., chloramine-T itself, or *p*-toluenesulphochloramide or dichloramine-T or hypochlorite ion which are the hydrolytic products¹⁰ of the parent material.

The amount of each species depends on the pH of the solution¹¹. At high alkali concentration, dichloramine-T does not exist and *p*-toluene sulphochloramide being a fairly strong acid ($pK_a = 4.55$)¹² exists in traces only. The two oxidising species left are thus chloramine-T and hypochlorite ion. The possibility of hypochlorite ion as the oxidising species is ruled out as it would imply an interaction between two negatively charged ions (enol anion and hypochlorite ion) which would correspond to a highly

negative entropy of activation, high energy of activation and a positive salt effect. The observed data and the thermodynamic parameter do not point to such a reaction path. Thus it is concluded that chloramine-T is the only oxidising species.

It is known that ketones enolise in alkaline solutions and this enol anion may react with chloramine-T to form an intermediate in a slow and rate determining step followed by its reaction with another molecule of chloramine-T in a faster step to give the corresponding 1,2-diketone. Thus

Applying steady state treatment to both the enol anion and the intermediate and taking a reasonable approximation $k_{-1} \gg k_2$ [chloramine-T], the rate law obtained is

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Chloramine-T}] = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} [\text{Chloramine-T}][\text{Cyclopentanone}][\text{OH}^-] \dots \text{(v)}$$

It is thus seen that the proposed mechanism gives a rate law consistent with the experimental observations.

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